

Authentic Arab Architecture

The search for authenticity in the Arab identity of architecture has long preoccupied the minds of many architects, taking on various forms and expressions. Some have clung to Arab and Islamic heritage, adorning modern buildings with traditional ornamentation. Others have shaped entire structures based on these decorative motifs. Some have deeply studied the past to recreate its designs with a modern twist, while others have chosen to detach from modern cities altogether, retreating to the countryside to rebuild and reshape society starting with its architecture.

All of these efforts stem from the urgent need to answer a fundamental question and respond to a pressing challenge. We must value these attempts, for they affirm the legitimacy and importance of the topic: our heritage must continue to shape our future without rupture or alienation from our past.

This subject has occupied the core of my focus over the past ten years. I was keen, early in my journey, to first study modern architectural schools deeply before diving into Arab architecture—so as not to be driven solely by emotional attachment to the legacy of Islamic civilization.

Through my research journey, I found that the dilemma lies in identifying a true starting point—one that builds on solid, authentic ground. In this article, I will focus on that foundation: the **differences in how "environment" is understood**, which I will explore further through a series of articles on the methods for seeking authentic Arab architecture.

The Western Concept of Environment

The differences between Western and Eastern civilizations are neither superficial nor merely formal. The perspective that shapes Western modernist architecture is fundamentally different from that which shaped Arab architecture. If we look at the English term “*environment*,” it is defined as a collection of biological, chemical, and physical elements surrounding a living organism or group of organisms, influencing their existence and survival.

This scientific lens dominates the Western definition—viewing the environment from an external perspective, judging both humans and non-human entities equally as “things” interacting and affecting one another. This view can be traced back to Renaissance thought, particularly Descartes’ dualism between subject and object, encapsulated in “*I think, therefore I am.*”

From this material-scientific viewpoint, the environment becomes a universal, uniform concept for all beings. The modernist rejection of dualism eliminated mediation between subject and object, favoring a singular scientific gaze and imposing abstraction across contexts. Mies van der Rohe called it “*universal space.*” This abstract geometry was embodied in what Philip Johnson called “*The International Style*” in the 1930s—where the same parallel lines were replicated globally.

Postmodernism, too, was not much more than a repackaged extension of the same principle, replacing modernist determinism with eclecticism. The result, as Rem Koolhaas calls it, is “*junkspace*”—a condition he ironically exploited for personal gain. Architects became transcendental figures, asserting ego through isolated architectural statements, ignoring urban fabric—when in truth, architecture must begin with history and environment.

The Arab Concept of Environment

In contrast, the Arabic word for *environment* is “البيئة” —literally meaning “**the home**” or “**the condition/state.**” Though concise, this definition fuses the natural, social, and symbolic environments into a unified view, with the human self at its center—never abstracted or excluded.

The “home” evokes belonging and containment—it gains meaning through human presence. “State” (ḥāl) unifies us with our environment, implying that our condition mirrors that of our surroundings—ever-changing, alive, and in constant becoming. It is a cross-domain term encompassing personal, spatial, and social dimensions. From this understanding, we see that the organic earthen cities of the Arab world were natural extensions of this perspective.

There was no sense of domination over the land. Rather, there was passion, care, and belonging. The Arab sought to understand the features of the land—studying every detail, interacting with it, being shaped by it, and reshaping it in return. It was a relationship of mutual growth, not alienation; of inclusion, not conflict.

How Can We Redraw Our Relationship with the Environment Through Our Own Worldview?

From our unique perspective, we see existence as a dynamic, momentary coupling between two halves: the individual and their environment. Human reality is born from this intimate union. To understand ourselves and our environments authentically, we must trace the process by which the human mediates their presence within the tangible world.

A clear example of this concept is the **purebred Arabian horse**, a symbol of pride across Arab history. Horses originally came from Asian nomads and were later acquired by Arabs. Though horses spread across the globe, taking on various characteristics, what made the **Arabian horse** so distinct? What defines its *authenticity*?

We find that the value of things is tied to their rarity and relevance within a specific environment. The Arab's lifestyle—rooted in travel, battle, trade, and long-distance movement—was deeply intertwined with the desert's harsh and unforgiving conditions. The Arabian horse distinguished itself by its *efficiency* in such circumstances—but more than that, by its **eloquence**.

Efficiency refers to mere functionality; eloquence includes emotional resonance. The horse's agility, speed, and war-readiness made it not only effective but also **aesthetic**—stirring emotion in its rider and inspiring imitation. It appeared in Arab poetry because it became a symbol born of Arab life and shaped by its landscape—a living reflection of identity.

Likewise, **authentic Arab architecture** reflects this interdependence. When Arabs entered Al-Andalus (Islamic Spain), they carried with them a refined sensitivity to beauty, life's resources, and the poetics of existence. Water, called "*blue gold*" by Arabs, was revered in dry climates. Plants, lightness, elegance, and poeticism were deeply felt, influenced by the horse and poetry alike.

We must also not forget the Arab's moral nobility and generosity of that time, which found architectural expression in **the Alhambra Palace**, in its slender columns and muqarnas that elevate the ceiling toward the heavens. These designs bore no resemblance to the massive, heavy architecture of other local cultures—despite both societies sharing the same environment. The Arab's sensitivity to nature elevated the architecture, and in turn, it elevated him.

This was a reciprocal relationship—an ongoing dance of being and becoming, where each reshaped the other.

Authenticity Cannot Be Bought or Designed

Authenticity is not a product to be bought or sold. It has no fixed style or ready-made architectural formula. It is a **way of being**—born from an individual's response to their environment and their evolving interaction with it across time. There is no meaning to modernity that does not take into account the worldview of its people and their way of life.

True modernity must grow from its own soil, shaped by the diversity of our lives and grounded in a sincere understanding of reality. We want to feel connected to the things around us. We need a **logical and existential revolution** to overcome Cartesian dualism.

This means respecting history and environment—not by slavishly mimicking past forms, but by creating **new forms of local mediation**, pursuing history instead of ignoring it or “*deep-freezing*” it.

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